

BIOCHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF MESOCYCLOPS LEUKARTI(CLAUS,1853) FROM NILWANDE DAM AKOLE TAHSIL.

Prof. Gadhawe Anuradha Atmaram
Arts, Commerce & Science College Alkuti
Tal: Parner, Dist : Ahmednagar
Pin No. 414305

Abstract:-

Zooplankton are small, floating as weakly swimming organisms. They are heterotrophic. Zooplankton is the important component of aquatic fauna which serves as a major component of aquatic food chain. The main role of zooplankton in ecosystem is to process energy and organic matter in food web. Zooplankton are cosmopolitan in nature and they are found in all freshwater. Zooplankton fauna consist of protozoa, Rotifera, Cladocera, Copepoda, Ostracoda. Copepoda are the largest group of crustacea comprising over 6000 species. Copepod refers to oar foot or paddle foot. The length is less than 2.00 mm long. Body is clearly segmented, less elongated, cylindrical. Head consist of two pair of antenna. The monoculture preparation for the estimation of glycogen, protein and lipid by De Zwaan Zandee, Lowery et al., and Lehtonen method respectively. Result shows that the glycogen content (37.21 ug/ml), protein (84.3ug/ml), and lipid (22.8 ug/ml) were obtained in *Mesocyclops leuckarti*. It was concluded that the present study helps to aware the budding researcher for the future investigation.

Key words: - Freshwater, Biochemical composition, *Mesocyclops leuckarti*

Introduction:

Zooplankton are cosmopolitan in nature and they are found to inhabit all freshwater tropical wetland. It plays an important role in recycling nutrients as well as cycling energy within their respective environment (Sulata et al., 2016). These are the main source of natural food for fish which is directly related to their survival and growth and are base of food chain and food web in all aquatic ecosystem. (Miah et al., 2013). Zooplankton is a good indicator of change in physical and chemical conditions as well as environmental condition (Sulata et al., 2016). Zooplankton are microscopic animal. They feed on phytoplankton which directly provide food source for larval vertebrates and invertebrates. Zooplankton fauna consist of Rotifera, Cladocera, Copepoda, Ostracoda. These are free floating animals (Rajagopal et al., 2010). The environmental factors and characters of water have great importance upon growth of zooplankton, hence the water quality influence zooplankton abundance (Suresh et al., 2011). Copepods are present in most aquatic habitats. They constitute the most important link between pelagic primary producer and higher trophic levels in marine food webs (Turner, 2004). The species of copepods have limited visual capabilities and restricted to chemosensory and hydro-mechanical information to perceive their surrounding (Folt and Goldman, 1981, Heuch et al., 2007). Copepod having main two groups Calanoid and Cyclopoid. They have 13 distinct life stages (i.e. egg, six naupliar stages, five copepodite stages, adult) and many species are sexually dimorphic. Copepods are subclass 0.5 to 2 mm many copepod species ranging from in size. They having jointed appendages and segmented body (Kevin W.H. Kwok et al., 2015). Copepod are common zooplankton of freshwater and brackish water. Zooplankton constitute important food source of many omnivorous and carnivorous fishes and also support the necessary amount of protein for the rapid growth of larval carps (Rahman, et al., 2008). Zooplankton maintains proper equilibrium between biotic and abiotic component of the aquatic ecosystem.

Material and Method:

Zooplankton sample was collected from Nilwande Dam, also called upper Pravara Dam, in the Indian state of Maharashtra is the second largest dam on Pravara river. The dam is located near Akole, Ahmednagar district. The height of the dam above lowest foundation is 73.91m (242.5 fit) while the length is 583m (1913 fit). The sample is collected by using plankton net (40µm mesh size) in between 6 pm to 9pm because zooplankton are photosensitive. The sample then transferred into 50 ml plastic sample bottle and brought to laboratory for further analysis. The primary analysis is done by using light microscope. The Copepod species was identified by using zooplankton identification key. The identified Copepod species were isolated and cultured in glass tank, (6x6 inches). The isolated species was used for monoculture. The sample is filtered by using Whatman filter paper and it dried for up to 7-8 days at room temperature. After drying sample is collected in small Eppendorf tube. This sample is used for estimation of glycogen, protein and lipid. The glycogen is estimated by De Zwaan and Zandee, 1972 Method, Estimation of total protein by Lowery et al., 1951 method and lipid is estimated by Lehtonen, 1996 methods respectively.

Result:

Carbohydrates plays role in cellular biochemistry, it is structural and functional unit of food reserves. The glycogen (Trehalose) content of Copepod species was $37.21 \pm 0.7 \mu\text{g/ml}$ (Table.1 and Figure.4) Protein formed the major biochemical constituent in Copepod species.

Zooplankton utilize the protein as an additional source of energy at the time of stress. The protein content of cultured Copepod species was $84.3 \pm 0.42 \mu\text{g/ml}$ (Table.1 and Figure.4) Lipid are major source of energy. It involve in storage energy, signalling and acting as structural component of cell membrane. The lipid content of Copepod species was $22.8 \pm 0.15 \mu\text{g/m}$. (Table.1 and Figure.4) .

Overall study shows that protein found to be in high amount ($84.3 \pm 0.42 \mu\text{g/ml}$) followed by glycogen in moderate amount ($37.21 \pm 0.7 \mu\text{g/ml}$) and least amount ($22.8 \pm 0.15 \mu\text{g/ml}$) of lipid in Copepod species.

Parameters	Carbohydrates (Treehouse) µg/ml	Protein µg/ml	Lipids µg/ml
Zooplanktons Species			
Copepod Species	37.21 ± 0.7	84.3 ± 0.42	22.8 ± 0.15

Table.1 Biochemical Composition of *Mesocyclops leukarti* during study period Values are average of triplicate sample (Mean ± S.D.)

Figure.2 Biochemical Composition of *Mesocyclops leukarti* during study period

Discussion:

The Biochemical composition of zooplankton like protein, carbohydrates and lipid are play important role in storage, transport, mechanical support, growth, source of energy, cellular biochemistry (Kale, 2002, Rao et al.,1980, Holden 1972, Villalan et al., 1990).In present study protein content of *Mesocyclops luekarti* was high ($84.3 \pm 0.42 \mu\text{g/ml}$) where as in the study of other authors (Arak and Mokashe, 2014) total protein content was 81.3 ± 0.01 . Mokashe et al., 2014 Bhat and Wagh, 1992 studied on biochemical composition, seasonal variation in biochemical composition of zooplankton are due to variable species composition and their population, because of short life span. They found that protein values are relatively lower.

In present study glycogen content of *Mesocyclops luekarti* was $37.21 \pm 0.7 \mu\text{g/ml}$. Carbohydrate content was found to be low in earlier study of Madhupratap and Venugopal et al., 1979). It was about 0.39 and 4.18 % in terms of dry weight, in tropical estuarine region. Shaikh et al., 2017 found that carbohydrate content in *Mesocyclops luekarti* was 18.10 ± 0.24 % dry weight. During the study of biochemical composition of Discussion Page 16 zooplankton in West coast of India. Carbohydrates ranges from 5.83 to 14.98 % maximum carbohydrates percentage recorded in Kannur region, because of multi diatomaceous bloom are present. Carbohydrate content of this study is higher than the earlier report (Jadadeesan et al., 2010). According to Goswami et al., 1981, carbohydrate content was generally poor.

In present study content of lipid in *Mesocyclops luekarti* was lower $22.8 \pm 0.15 \mu\text{g/ml}$. The lipid content recorded in study of Sreepada et al, 1992 was 4.48 % to 20.45 %. The lipid content in tropical zooplankton as compared to temperate zooplankton significantly low. According to Dube et al., 2017 total lipid was highest in *Mesocyclops luekarti* ($20.8 \pm 0.2\%$) followed by *Brachionus calyciflorus* ($16.66 \pm 0.09\%$) and least in Moinamicura (8.7 ± 0.14 %). Lipid are second major component in zooplankton recorded in study of Jagadeesan, 2010; which was ranged from 11.02 to 19.67%. Lipid was stored for purpose of energy reserve in emergency period.

Overall study indicates that the selected species of Copepod (*Mesocyclops leukarti*) has great amount of protein, carbohydrate and lipid.

Conclusion:

The present study concluded that the zooplankton (*Mesocyclops leukarti*) from Nilwande dam, AkoleTahasil are found to be rich in protein, carbohydrates, lipid source. In present study protein found to be in highest concentration where in the lipid is in least amount and carbohydrates in moderate concentration. Copepod species are rich in protein content they can use live feed in the field of aquaculture. They play important role in food chain of aquatic ecosystem. Eventually, it is concluded that the Copepod species from Nilwande dam provided abundant source of biochemical composition which will useful as live food for fishes. Hence this is the great benefit in fishery industry to increase fishery production

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